

EARTH-MOON OBSERVATION CUBESAT SYSTEM. U. N. A. N. Sonou⁵, M. Raouf^{1,2}, B. Foing^{1,2}, F. Fazel Hesar^{2,3}, P. R. Mitra⁴, P. Ananwatananyoo⁴, A. R. pacheco⁵, C. Irakleous³, B. Cameron¹ and E. Woestl¹.

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Introduction: The advent of CubeSat technology has significantly reduced barriers to space exploration, enabling new opportunities for satellite-based Earth observation and lunar analysis. This project focuses on the development of two advanced 3U CubeSat missions: one for Earth observation in low Earth orbit (LEO) and another for lunar analysis. The lunar mission comprises two components: a rover operating on the lunar surface and a CubeSat positioned at the Earth-Moon L2 point. Both are equipped with hyperspectral imagers, aiming to capture detailed imagery to study the Moon's mineral composition and geological history.

The objective of this work is to seamlessly integrate these sophisticated systems into the CubeSat architecture, maximizing mission efficiency and performance. This involves identifying the necessary subsystems, integrating them effectively, and creating a prototype to demonstrate the feasibility of this concept.

The Earth-observation CubeSat will utilize high-resolution cameras and multispectral sensors to gather critical environmental data, enhancing our ability to monitor ecological changes and understand Earth's ecosystems. For the lunar mission, the rover will use the hyperspectral imager to scan the lunar surface for minerals, while the CubeSat at EML2 will conduct a detailed analysis of the lunar environment, providing essential data for planning future lunar exploration and resource utilization.

The success of these missions hinges on the integration of the hyperspectral imager with subsystems like the Attitude Determination and Control System (ADCS), the Communication System, and the Power System. These subsystems must work harmoniously to ensure accurate data capture and transmission. This work involves assessing the integration of the hyperspectral imager with other subsystems and identifying the most critical subsystems for mission success. This includes conducting camera tests using a Raspberry Pi camera to evaluate its potential for hyperspectral imaging, analyzing spectral data, and

comparing its performance with that of a spectrometer planned for the prototype.

The findings from this work will contribute to the advancement of CubeSat technology for Earth observation and lunar analysis, showcasing the potential of small satellites in advancing space exploration and environmental monitoring.

Fig 1: System Diagram of the LEO Cubesat

References:

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